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Effect of Dynamic Capabilities on Organizational Resilience: A Study on the Manufacturing Pharmaceutical Companies in Egypt

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Abstract

Purpose: *The paper aims to answer the research question “To what extent is there an effect of sensing capability, seizing capability, and reconfiguration capability on organizational resilience in manufacturing pharmaceutical companies in Egypt?”.*

Design/methodology/ approach: *This research used a quantitative approach by surveying a valid sample of 134 pharmaceutical manufacturing companies through a structured questionnaire. The data was collected from decision-makers from top management representing these companies.*

Findings: *The results confirmed the effect of Dynamic Capabilities (DCs) represented by sensing, seizing, and reconfiguring dimensions on Organizational Resilience (OR).*

Originality/ value: *This research adds to the organizational resilience literature and attempts to guide Egyptian pharmaceutical manufacturing companies to foster their dynamic capabilities to enhance organizational resilience.*

Paper type: *Research paper*

Keywords: *Dynamic capabilities, sensing, seizing, reconfiguration, strategic resilience, organizational resilience.*

1. Introduction

Nowadays the world suffers from various environmental turbulences whether market turbulence or technological turbulence. Accordingly, organizations must manage these turbulences by capturing opportunities or avoiding crises and threats. Moreover, there are geopolitical turbulences that have affected various countries worldwide such as Russia and Ukraine, Gaza and Israel, the Red Sea wars, and recently the situation in Syria. On the other hand, the COVID-19 pandemic crisis, and successive terrorist attacks are additional disturbances. All these disruptive events have negative impacts on most countries and consequently, organizations suffer from these wars, turbulences, and negative situations. Hence, organizations should exploit their Dynamic Capabilities (DCs) to generate adaptive reactions and responses to such crises or negative impacts (Hussain and Malik, 2022). Additionally, they added that sensing, seizing, and reconfiguring capabilities are the main dimensions of DCs that make the organization able to reach Organizational Resilience (OR) during environmental turbulences. So, OR is an important management concept that enables organizations to react quickly based on their prediction and adaptation abilities before the incident occurs (Akpan et al., 2022). In

other words, OR prompts organizations to achieve continuous development to cope with environmental changes.

This study investigates the relationship between two constructs of dynamic capabilities (DCs) and organizational resilience (OR).

2. Literature Review

2.1 Dynamic Capabilities

Dynamic capabilities (DCs) theory is the extension of resource-based view (RBV) according to the essential work of Teece et al., (1997), and supported by other scholars (Awwad et al., 2022; Piotr, 2015). Additionally, Qiu et al. (2022) viewed DCs as being established by resources, processes, methods, systems, and competencies of organizations that intentionally integrate, build, and reconfigure external and internal resources to deal with environmental changes. So, DCs were considered an important approach to achieve a long-term sustainable competitive edge rather than the RBV model.

Kurrtmollaiev (2020) stated that the essential work of Teece et al. (1997) is the main base to understand DCs, defined as the organizational ability to consolidate, unify, build, and reconstruct/ reconfigure their internal and external competencies to react to quick changes in the market. Thus, DCs are essential factors for developing an organization's competitive advantages based on the market position. Moreover, Zahra et al. (2006) conceptualized DCs as being the capabilities of organizations to reconstruct and reconfigure their routines, and resources appropriately by their decision-makers. Over the years, DCs have been developed to describe them as a practice of organizations; while learning and knowledge play a vital role in guiding and generating organizational routines. So, some researchers viewed DCs as a group of processes and practices (Gremme & Wohlgemuth, 2017).

However, Halfat et al. (2007) viewed DCs as the strength of an organization to increase, produce, or allocate its resources. In other words, it is the capability of renewing, developing, or modifying its resources (Gremme & Wohlgemuth, 2017).

This study adopts the definition of DCs according to Teece (2007) and is supported by Betchel et al., (2023). This definition divided DCs into three capabilities: sensing, seizing, and reconfiguring. Also, they added that these capabilities (domains) are assorted by rapidly changing events, and they conceptualized them from a strategic perspective. Sensing capability is the organization's ability to identify opportunities and threats; seizing is the capability of capturing invaluable opportunities and minimizing the impact of environmental threats; and reconfiguring refers to the organizational capability of sustaining its competitive advantages by protecting, modifying, and improving its intangible and tangible resources. Several authors supported this same classification of DCs according to Teece's (2007) model (Ambrosini & Bowman 2009; Easterby-Smith & Prieto 2008; Hodgkinson & Healey, 2011; Gremme & Wohlgemuth, 2017; Priyono and Hidayat, 2022). All these capabilities enhance the ability of organizations to adapt to changes in the market. Moreover, Kump et al. (2018) proved the validation of these three dimensions of DCs. Additionally, Teece (2014) emphasized that these dimensions must be closely related to organizational strategy whereas Awwad et al. (2022) pointed out that they should be jointly applied.

Sensing capability: Kump et al. (2018) stated that sensing is the ability of an organization to focus on internal and external changes that will lead to determining opportunities and forecasting unpredictable situations and threats. So, they called this dimension a prediction capability or, the organizational capacity for screening the market for existing opportunities, threats, and challenges, so that organizations can predict customer needs according to the market changes (Priyono & Hidayat, 2022). Aldianto et al. (2021) added that an organization should identify and assess unexpected events and opportunities that can occur in markets, and called this stage screening.

Seizing capability: Priyono and Hidayat (2022) considered it as a second dimension of DCs. Teece (2007) stated that the seizing dimension is the organizational ability to capture invaluable opportunities for firm growth, while Kump et al. (2018) called seizing a strategic decision because it is built according to the collection and filtration of data. Hence, this dimension makes an organization capable of achieving and enhancing its strengths to meet or adjust its strategic objectives as well as avoid and minimize the impact of threats or weaknesses (Teece, 2007).

Reconfiguring capability: tends to reorganize the organizational capabilities, resources, and structures for the accomplishment of organizational competitive advantage (Teece, 2007). He meant not only tangible but also intangible resources, whereas Kump et al. (2018) stated that it shows the power of organizations to make decisions to enhance and develop their business model, products, and methods. Hence, this dimension is represented in the organization's attempt to modify and adapt its resources to sustain its position and growth in the market (Priyono & Hidayat, 2022). Therefore, Teece (2014) stated this dimension is very important for updating the competencies of an organization.

2.2 Organizational Resilience (OR)

OR is considered multifaceted and multidimensional as researchers adopted it through many perspectives and fields (Khan et al., 2019; Duchek, 2020; Ma et al., 2018), conceptualizing it as dynamic capabilities and flexibility of organizations to predict, adapt, and learn efficiently during jolts. Ishak & Williams (2018) proposed that OR is a dynamic process that includes organizations trying to react and adapt rapidly to challenges and external environments. However, Gittell et al. (2006) adopted it from the outcome perspective where they considered that OR is achieved by adaptation and modifications taken to mitigate crises and disruptive events.

Accordingly, many authors defined OR as per their perspectives and respective fields. When organizations need to successfully handle and solve plentiful unpredictable adversities, then OR is shown as a desirable solution (Luthans et al., 2010; Shin et al., 2012). However, Chen et al. (2021) defined the OR as the organizational capability of foreseeing disruptive events, resisting them, and trying to adapt rapidly by reorganizing and realigning resources and procedures, reshaping the network of organizations, recovering rapidly, and using the disruptive events to accomplish countertrend growth. Therefore Ruiz-Martin et al. (2018) confirmed that the importance of OR is increased according to the high awareness of adversity impact and the rapid environmental changes like technological, economic, and geopolitical turbulences.

Xie, et al. (2018) showed that OR consists of three main capabilities such as resistance, reorientation, and recovery capabilities; each one is referred to as respectively facing disruptive events, jolts or adversities, and trying to recover from any disruption and getting back again to the equilibrium state. The nature of OR is the result of an interaction between the organization and environmental turbulences (Williams et al., 2017). So, organizations need to show efficient reactions to resist crises or negative events and deal with them after such incidents occur and not only before or during their occurrence. Moreover, Duchek (2020) proposed that OR consists of three sequential and interdependent phases; anticipation, coping, and adaption phases to face a current crisis. Boin & Eeten (2013) stated that during an "anticipation phase"; organizations should be ready and prepared against any negative events... In the next phase "coping phase", organizations try to assess and accept the adverse events and think about how to deal with and react against them. So, it is called the absorption stage; the organization readjusts its resources, routines, and procedures (Lengnick-Hall et al., 2011). In the "adaptation phase", organizations must deal with crises and get countermeasures to resist (Duchek, 2020). Chen et al. (2021) stated that the adaptation phase includes many changes that are due to growth. So, they considered it as an advancement stage. Additionally, they proposed that OR should include a recovery phase. Also, Falk et al. (2019) supported that the recovery stage is one of methodical procedures besides reorganization and resistance in the face of crisis.

Hence, according to the fundamental research of some authors like Chen et al. (2021), Duchek (2020) Falk et al. (2019), and Ma et al. (2018), OR has specific and essential capabilities such as anticipation, absorption, adaptation, and recovery. Thus, OR should include not only three phases but also four phases. Also, OR is considered a dynamic process (Ishak & Williams, 2018); McCarthy et al, 2017). They stated that OR phases are very close and interconnected to each other, or more specifically they are associated and overlapping with each other.

Pal et al. (2014) proposed that OR consists of four components: agility, redundancy, robustness, and networking. Somers (2009) confirmed that these components are the core of OR. Also, Burnard and Bhamra (2011) described them as the development core of an organization and its stability to perform well in times of turbulence.

Kantur and Iseri-Say (2015) considered agility as an important factor of OR. They defined it as the capacity of organizations to react quickly and flexibly to environmental changes, allowing managers in organizations to make decisions effectively and rapidly. Also, it is considered a vital characteristic of OR because of the quick modifications and strong responses that should be taken (Akpan et al., 2022). Robustness is the strength of the system to resist stress incidence, adapt to changes, and operate without degeneration (Duchek, 2020). Moreover, it is a resistance capability to withstand and absorb the impacts of turbulence and deal with them, then organizations recover and get back again in their position in the market (Kantur & Iseri-Say, 2015). Pal et al. (2014) claimed that redundancy is important to enable OR to be achieved by using all resources of the organization. It was described as a capability of decision-making and executing alternative actions or strategies (Lengnick-Hall et al., 2011). The last one of the OR components is networking capability which, according to Pal et al. (2014), is the level of transparency and interaction. So, it supports trustability, information flow, investment, and cooperative decision-making at the organizational level. Using networking capability enables organizations to obtain a lot of information, and goods that are considered essential to survive and expand during crises or negative situations (Mcentire, 2012).

2.3 Relationship between Sensing Capability and Organizational Resilience

Khan et al. (2019) proved that sensing is an essential and necessary capability of OR. Vogus and Sutcliffe (2007) stated that organizations use sensing to screen the market to collect essential information and merge it into their knowledge sources. Jiang et al. (2021) confirmed that sensing is required to identify opportunities and threats in the market. Moreover, Martinelli et al. (2018) confirmed the effective roles of the sensing dimension on OR during negative circumstances through their qualitative research. Accordingly, this research proposed the following hypothesis.

H1: *Sensing capability has a positive effect on the organizational resilience of pharmaceutical manufacturing companies in Egypt.*

2.4 Relationship between Seizing Capability and Organizational Resilience

Hussain & Malik (2022) found that seizing capability leads to organizational resilience through agility and plays a mediator role. Kähkönen et al. (2023) confirmed in their research the relationship between seizing dimension and supply chain resilience. Similarly, Jiang et al. (2021) stated that adaptation capability is linked to seizing capability to hold all suitable opportunities during a crisis. Hence, the second hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H2: *Seizing capability has a positive effect on the organizational resilience of pharmaceutical manufacturing companies in Egypt.*

2.5 Relationship between Reconfiguring Capability and Organizational Resilience

Reconfiguration capability is vital to sustaining an organization's competitive edge during modification and challenges, and it makes organizations more resilient (Jiang et al., 2021). Also, it helps to build OR through

negative circumstances, by combining routine interactions to accomplish flexibility and enabling a stable state for organizations (Manfield & Newey, 2018). Moreover, Akpan et al. (2022) confirmed a positive relationship between reconfiguration capability and OR. Parker and Ameen (2018) supported these findings and stated that this dimension enables OR to be achieved. Additionally, in service sectors like the tourism sector Hussain and Malik (2022) found that reconfiguration helps to achieve OR proposing the supply chain agility as a mediating variable. Based on these findings, the third hypothesis is proposed:

H3: *Reconfiguring capability has a positive effect on the organizational resilience of pharmaceutical manufacturing companies in Egypt.*

3. Research Design and Methodology

3.1 Conceptual Framework

This research proposes that Dynamic Capabilities as an independent variable, composed of three dimensions; sensing, seizing, and reconfiguring have a positive effect on the dependent variable Organizational Resilience. Figure 1 shows the relationship between research variables based on the previously formulated hypotheses.

Figure 1: The Conceptual Framework

Source: developed by researcher

This research adopts a positivism philosophy to investigate the proposed hypotheses. Also, it adopts a deductive quantitative survey method. Additionally, a descriptive approach is proposed to achieve the research objectives. Cohen et al. (2011) supported that the survey approach is preferable as it provides quantitative data about respondents and their experiences and gives answers to research questions.

3.2 Population and Sampling

Egypt has a total of 176 pharmaceutical manufacturing companies, all of which hold a license to manufacture pharmaceutical products as per the Egyptian Drug Authority (December 2023). A non-probability approach is adopted by using a convenient sampling technique. The target sample size of this research is 121 companies with a confidence level of 95% and a margin of error is 5% (Sekaran and Bougies, 2019). Each company is represented by one respondent of managerial level with at least one year experience in the same company.

3.3 Data Collection Instrument

A Questionnaire was compiled to measure the research variables. The questionnaire consists of 38 questions divided into three sections. The first section represents the control variable consisting of two questions, the second section includes questions measuring the three dimensions of dynamic capabilities and adopted from Kump et al., (2018). Sensing capabilities consist of six statements, seizing capability includes four statements, and reconfiguring capabilities include six statements. The last section includes twenty statements to measure Organization Resilience, adopted from Akpan et al., (2022); Kantur & Iseri-Say, (2015); Pal et al., (2014). A 5-Point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree is adopted.

4. Statistical Analysis and Findings

The questionnaire was distributed and delivered to 153 from 176 manufacturing companies. The researcher obtained 134 valid responses showing a response rate of 87.6%.

Using SPSS is a powerful software statistical tool to analyze and test data collection for this research. Normality, correlation, and reliability tests are conducted on the valid sample to gain beneficial insights about the relationship between sensing, seizing, reconfiguring capabilities, and organizational resilience.

4.1 Reliability Test

The reliability test shows that Cronbach's Alpha coefficient exceeded the cutoff point of 0.7 for all four variables: seizing, reconfiguring, sensing, and organizational resilience indicating a high consistency, interrelated, and high reliability as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Reliability test results

No.	Variables	No. of Items	Reliability Coefficient by Cronbach's alpha
1	Organizational Resilience	20	0.933
2	Sensing	6	0.863
3	Seizing	4	0.735
4	Reconfiguring	6	0.774

4.2 Correlation Test

Correlation analysis at 0.01 level confirmed a positive significant relationship between sensing capability, seizing, and reconfiguring capability and organizational resilience. The strongest effect is reconfiguration, followed by sensing and finally seizing capabilities. Then OR showed a significant correlation and positive relation with reconfiguring, sensing, and seizing ($\rho = 0.623, 0.572, 0.511$) and reconfiguring respectively. So, these results of correlation tests give important insights indicating that these three dimensions of DCs are integrated, closed, and interconnected to each other with OR. (See table 2) This indicated that organizations should develop and focus their DCs to build organization resilience concept within internal strategies. Also, these three capabilities contribute to and are strong supporters of OR. It is also noted that sensing capability has a strong correlation with seizing capability ($\rho = 0.633, p < 0.001$), and has a moderate correlation with reconfiguring capability ($\rho = 0.518, p < 0.001$). Additionally, there are correlation between seizing and reconfiguring capabilities ($\rho = 0.458, p < 0.001$). Finally, all capabilities are interconnected and interrelated to each other within DCs.

Table 2: Correlation test results

		Correlations				
		Organization Resilience	Sensing Capability	Seizing Capability	Reconfiguring Capability	
Spearman's rho	Organization	Correlation	1.000	.572**	.511**	.623**

	Resilience	Coefficient				
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000	.000	.000
		N	134	134	134	134
	Sensing Capability	Correlation Coefficient	.572**	1.000	.633**	.518**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	.000	.000
		N	134	134	134	134
	Seizing Capability	Correlation Coefficient	.511**	.633**	1.000	.485**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.	.000
		N	134	134	134	134
	Reconfiguring Capability	Correlation Coefficient	.623**	.518**	.485**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.
		N	134	134	134	134

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

4.3 Regression Test

A regression test was conducted between each of the three independent variables, and one dependent variable by Model Summary and Anova. As shown in Tables 3, 4, and 5

Table 3: Model Summary table

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.783 ^a	0.613	0.604	0.45167	0.613	68.519	3	130	.000
a. Predictors: (Constant), Reconfiguration, Sensing, and Seizing Capabilities									

Table 4: Anova table

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	41.935	3	13.978	68.519	.000 ^b
	Residual	26.521	130	0.204		
	Total	68.455	133			
a. Dependent Variable: OR						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Reconfiguration, Sensing, and Seizing Capabilities.						

Table 5: Coefficient table

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	0.217	0.25		0.868	0.387

	Sensing Capability	0.249	0.078	0.247	3.188	0.002
	Seizing Capability	0.142	0.077	0.144	1.843	0.068
	Reconfiguration Capability	0.530	0.068	0.518	7.759	0.000
a. Dependent Variable: Organization Resilience						

According to the previous results of the regression test, the following findings are stated.

Hypothesis (H1) is accepted. As the regression test confirmed a significant positive relationship between sensing and OR, because of p -value = 0.02 and Beta = 0.247. This indicates that when OR is increased, also, sensing capability is increased. Therefore, sensing capability is considered an important variable to enhance OR, consequently, organizations are capable of withstanding negative impacts and turbulence by deploying sensing capability.

Hypothesis (H2) is accepted, with Beta 0.144 and p -value of 0.068. Then seizing has a positive effect OR but the significance level is a little above 0.05 = 0.068. Showing a moderate relationship between them. In other words, there is confirmation of this hypothesis but not as strong as sensing and reconfiguring capabilities.

Hypothesis (H3) is strongly accepted, as there is a strong positive and significant relationship between reconfiguring capability and OR, with Beta = 0.518 and p -value = 0.000. This shows that reconfiguration has a powerful effect on OR and it is the strongest predictor as compared with sensing and seizing capabilities.

5. Discussion

Based on the findings, dynamic capabilities consisting of three dimensions are positively related to organizational resilience. This means that DCs are important to achieve high levels of OR. These results conform with the qualitative research of Jiang et al. (2021) and Khan et al. (2019) who found that DCs through their three capabilities are very important to face and resist disruptive events.

However, these findings contradict Eisenhardt and Martin (2000) who claimed that the DCs are not essential to enhance resilience, and there is no direct relation between them. However, the findings of this research confirmed that organizational resilience is enhanced directly by applying all components of DCs (sensing, seizing, and reconfiguring). On manufacturing companies in Egypt. Such positive relationships explain that DCs enhance and improve OR levels within pharmaceutical companies. Therefore, pharmaceutical manufacturing companies need to foster using their resources and capabilities to build and strengthen OR to face any challenges efficiently.

Additionally, the findings are aligned with Akpan et al. (2022) research which proved that sensing and reconfiguring only are essential capabilities for OR. However, they applied their study on 11 manufacturing companies, and confirmed the necessity of two capabilities to enhance OR. However, the present study adopted three capabilities not two, and can be considered as an extension of this research.

6. Conclusion and Recommendation

This research investigates the relationship between DCs and OR, adopting DCs' three dimensions: sensing, seizing, and reconfiguring, to measure their respective effect on OR. The study is applied to pharmaceutical manufacturing companies in Egypt.

The empirical evidence of this research proved and supported that three capabilities magnify the level of organizational resilience to resist and mitigate crises. Such organizational resilience is reflected positively in companies' performance.

Accordingly, there are some recommendations based on this empirical research:

- a. Manufacturing companies in the pharmaceutical industry in Egypt need to focus efficiently on their capabilities to predict invaluable opportunities and possible challenges. So, this enables companies to adapt their resources rapidly to overcome negative circumstances.
- b. Managers with decision-making authority need to deploy and exploit dynamic capabilities to monitor, adapt, and react swiftly to market changes.
- c. Companies should exploit their current internal competencies with newly acquired capabilities in creative ways. This will achieve higher levels of organizational resilience which leads to improved manufacturing of products and overall performance.

7. Limitations and Recommendations for Future Study:

This study concentrated on the pharmaceutical industry as part of the industrial sector and did not focus on other sectors such as oil and gas, food and beverages, software, technology, and banking among others. It is suggested to carry out future studies in other manufacturing and service sectors.

Also, Organizational resilience should be investigated from a financial perspective to examine its effect on organizational performance. Furthermore, it is preferable to conduct future research to test this relationship through quantitative as well as qualitative and longitudinal research to gain more insights and details.

Additionally, it is recommended to use a larger sample size, preferably a probability random technique to allow the generalizability of results.

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